

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union

Synthesis Table on soil carbon data generators/repositories of European capabilities

Author: Mollenhauer, H.

Co-authors: Fantappie, M.; Marques, K.; Miguel-Lago, M.; Rajewicz, P.; Xu, H.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18978365

Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement n° 101112951.

www.project-credible.eu

DISCLAIMER: *The views expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views or position of the European Union. Neither the authors nor the CREDIBLE consortium are responsible for the use which might be made of the information contained in here.*

Table of content

Executive summary	3
1. Introduction	4
Scope	4
Objectives	5
2. Synthesis Table	6
3. Discussion	9
Data Quality and Standardization	9
Integration and Compatibility	9
Strengths and Weaknesses	9
Gaps and Challenges	10
Implications for Policy and Research	10
Opportunities for Improvement	10
4. Conclusion	11
References	12

List of acronyms and abbreviations

API: Application Programming Interface
CAP: Common Agricultural Policy
CF: Carbon Farming
CRCF: Carbon Removal Certification Framework
EC: European Commission
EU: European Union
FMIS: Farm Management Information Systems
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
GHG: Greenhouse Gas
IACS: Integrated Administration and Control System
INSPIRE: Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community
ISO: International Organization for Standardization
LIPS: Land Parcel Identification System
LUCAS: Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey
ML: Machine Learning
MRV: Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification
SOC: Soil Organic Carbon

Executive summary

Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) is vital for climate mitigation, agriculture, and ecosystem health. As the EU advances the Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) regulation, reliable SOC assessment and monitoring is essential. This synthesis assesses ten major European data systems—including monitoring networks, farm platforms, and research infrastructures—highlighting their strengths and gaps.

While some systems offer high-quality, open data, many face issues with accessibility, interoperability, and standardization. Integration challenges and uneven coverage hinder effective Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV) and policy support.

The report recommends aligning data systems with CRCF regulation standards, supporting Application Programming Interface (API) development, and embedding scientific infrastructures into certification frameworks to improve data credibility, reduce costs, and support climate-smart land use.

1. Introduction

SOC is a cornerstone of terrestrial ecosystem functioning, agricultural productivity, and climate resilience. It plays a critical role in regulating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, supporting biodiversity, enhancing soil water-holding capacity, and maintaining soil fertility. In the context of climate change mitigation, increasing SOC stocks is a cost-effective and nature-based solution with strong co-benefits for food systems and ecosystem services. Consequently, improving our ability to monitor, report, and verify changes in SOC is essential for implementing robust Carbon Farming (CF) and soil restoration strategies under the EU Green Deal and the Soil Strategy for 2030.

Central to this effort are the diverse data generators and repositories that collect, curate, and disseminate information on soil carbon dynamics. These include long-term monitoring sites, laboratory networks, farm information systems, earth observation tools, and pan-European

databases. Together, these entities shape the foundation upon which MRV systems and carbon certification schemes—such as those under the EU CRCF —must be built. However, differences in methodology, accessibility, spatial coverage, and data quality across these systems create barriers to standardization and integration.

Scope

This synthesis focuses on the European landscape of soil carbon data infrastructures, emphasizing the need to coordinate and evaluate the various actors contributing to soil data generation, harmonization, and use. In light of increasing policy interest and financial support for climate-smart land management, it becomes imperative to assess both the capabilities and shortcomings of these systems. Standardizing, benchmarking, and linking these datasets across Member States will be key to ensuring consistency in carbon accounting and eligibility for result-based climate payments.

The table presented in this report compiles data from major public and private initiatives, regulatory frameworks, and scientific MRV projects, offering a comparative view of their strengths, accessibility, and relevance for CRCF-aligned monitoring.

Objectives

- Comprehensively map the main soil carbon data generators and repositories active in Europe.
- Compare and evaluate their respective capabilities, strengths, and integration with CRCF-compatible MRV frameworks.
- Identify gaps related to spatial coverage, data accessibility, standardization, and policy alignment to inform future research and system development.

This overview serves as a foundation for optimizing MRV pathways in the EU’s emerging CF ecosystem and supports evidence-based policymaking for soil health and climate mitigation.

2. Synthesis Table

Data Source / Technology	Ownership and Accessibility	Geographic Coverage and Activity Estimate	Data Type (SOC, Management, EO, etc.)	Role in CRCF MRV System	Technological Strengths	Current Gaps and Challenges	Recommendations for Enhancing CRCF Monitoring	Key Regulatory and Scientific References
Long-Term Monitoring (LTM) Networks	Public – Partial (not harmonized across MS)	EU-wide; ~570+ LTM sites	Direct soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks; land management history (tillage, crop rotation); climatic context via site metadata.	Used to calibrate and validate Tier 3 soil carbon models such as RothC and Century; supports baseline construction and contributes to uncertainty estimation; MRV projects (e.g., MRV4SOC, MARVIC, ORCASA) utilize LTM datasets for methodological validation and scenario modeling (e.g. direct measure the impact of CF practices, also evaluate the impact of climate change on CF practices).	Scientific credibility, provides long-term trends, supports calibration and validation of models	Limited site harmonization and representativity; many sites not under real farm management conditions; limited real-time integration with MRV tools like RS regarding the plot sizes.	Expand LTM to include more pedo-climatic zones under active farm management; build automated data feeds into CRCF registries; harmonize with MRV project frameworks (e.g., MRV4SOC). Integrate LTM inside a broader network of real farms in the form of lighthouses of living labs.	(EU/2024/3012, 2024; Xu et al., 2025)
Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS)	Private – Restricted (user-controlled sharing)	Pan-EU use; ~120+ FMIS vendors, 40–60% of farms	Tillage dates, cover crop usage, fertilization rates, seeding, harvest operations, input purchases linked to specific parcels via FMIS software.	Core for continuous data collection on tillage, fertilization, cover crops, and yields. Enables integration with MRV tools for automated monitoring. MRV projects use FMIS as an interface for harmonizing farm activity records and linking them to modeling platforms.	Detailed operational data, real-time farm-level granularity, widely adopted in commercial systems	Data fragmentation across vendors; lack of semantic and syntactic interoperability; privacy and licensing issues impede scaling for public MRV.	Create EU-wide FMIS interoperability standards; fund public-private data sharing agreements; integrate FMIS as a primary source of farm-level monitoring under CRCF Article 7.	(EU/2019/1024, 2019; Fantappiè et al., 2025)
Earth Observation (Copernicus, EO providers)	Mixed – Open (Copernicus) / Restricted (private)	EU-wide; Copernicus + 50+ private EO service providers	reflectance bands, NDVI, biomass indices, land cover classification maps, EO-derived SOC models, backscatter change detection.	Critical for scalable monitoring of biomass cover, land use change, and surface reflectance indices. MRV projects like AgriCarbon-EO and MRV4SOC assimilate EO inputs to improve SOC estimations and carbon stock change tracking.	High spatial and temporal resolution, EU-wide coverage, scalable for large areas	Spatial and temporal resolution gaps for cloud-prone areas; limited validation datasets for SOC estimation; insufficient integration into standard CRCF MRV models.	Enhance EO-SOC model calibration using long-term SOC plots and MRV pilot datasets; support multi-sensor fusion platforms; align EO layers with CRCF quantification tiers.	(EU/2024/3012, 2024; Miguel-Lago et al., 2024; Succurro et al., 2025; Wijmer et al., 2024)
Soil Laboratories (Public and Private)	Mixed – Fragmented (dependent on contracts)	National; ~300,000 soil samples/year	Lab-analyzed SOC content, bulk density, pH, texture, total nitrogen and C/N ratio using ISO 17025 certified methods.	Provides essential lab-verified SOC baselines and trend validation datasets. MRV projects push for standardization in bulk density and SOC lab analytics across regions for higher data comparability and accuracy.	Ground-truth measurements, standardized lab protocols (in public labs), precision in SOC quantification	Non-harmonized lab methods across countries; inconsistent metadata; lack of standardized sampling design; limited access to private lab results.	Establish EU-wide lab accreditation protocols for SOC MRV; create GDPR-compliant open lab data repositories; integrate with soil sample metadata standards.	(Fantappiè et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2025)

EU Soil Data Repositories (JRC, ESDAC)	Public – Open access (under licensing agreements)	EU-wide; ESDAC, LUCAS, SoilGrids datasets	Harmonized EU-wide SOC maps, land use change layers, climate and soil attributes (e.g., SoilGrids, LUCAS), with historical trend layers.	Reference source for EU-scale harmonized SOC and management data layers. Supports initial conditions for models used in MRV frameworks and facilitates cross-border calibration under CRCF.	Official reference datasets, harmonized across EU, supports policy and research alignment	Low spatial granularity (~1 km); outdated in some areas; insufficient for field-level CRCF certification; weak integration with parcel-level monitoring tools.	Downscale EU soil maps using farm-scale inputs; increase update frequency (bi-annual); embed SOC layers in CRCF digital MRV dashboards with machine-readable formats.	(EU/2007/2, 2007; Mal, 2025; Panagos et al., 2022)
Proximal Sensing Tools (e.g., spectroscopy)	Private – Restricted (mostly private or pilot-specific datasets)	EU-pilots; ~10 R&D systems, 50+ sensors in use	Spectral soil signatures from VIS-NIR-MIR sensors, proximal geospatial data layers, ground calibration values, dry/wet basis SOC estimates.	Allows rapid on-field assessment of SOC; supports frequent low-cost verification for CRCF MRV. Projects like SOILWISE and MRV4SOC work to calibrate these tools with lab data and modeling efforts.	Rapid, cost-effective SOC estimation; enables frequent, non-invasive monitoring	Variability in sensor calibration; no central EU library of spectral fingerprints; accuracy varies significantly across soil types, moisture levels, and across tools; variability in core methodology complicates harmonisation.	Build open-source library of sensor calibration profiles; support in situ calibration research; develop certification-compatible SOC estimation modules using proximal data with respective references.	(Poggio et al., 2021; Rajewicz & Atherton, 2025; Shocc & Swails, 2024)
CAP-related Systems (IACS, LPIS)	Public – regulatory compliance, but not always open format	EU Member States; Over 3 million parcels in IACS	Parcel geometry, crop declarations, rotation patterns, georeferenced CAP compliance data (e.g., eco-schemes participation).	Supplies geospatial anchors for field-level data reporting; essential for parcel identification in CRCF audit trails. MRV tools reference LPIS/IACS for spatial alignment of modeled results with CAP-compliant reporting.	Reliable spatial land parcel info; harmonized for CAP compliance; legal mandate ensures data availability	Not fully interoperable with CRCF MRV tools; siloed across Member States; temporal lags in updates; not always publically accessible in machine-readable format.	Mandate linkage of IACS data with CRCF reporting frameworks; automate parcel-based updates; create a central access point for MRV systems via CAP APIs.	(Arias-Navarro et al., 2024; EU/2021/2115, 2021; EU/2021/2116, 2021; EU/2024/3012, 2024; Tóth & Milenov, 2020; Xu et al., 2025)
Living Labs and Regional Initiatives	Mixed Project-based access (not centralized, varies regionally)	20+ regional labs; active in Horizon EU	Multi-actor datasets including farm practices, yields, biodiversity indicators, SOC trends, socio-economic insights, water management.	Living Labs act as MRV innovation hubs by testing, adapting, and co-developing monitoring solutions in varied agro-ecological zones. Project data from Horizon Europe pilots feed directly into CRCF methodology refinement.	Context-specific co-development, farmer-inclusive, supports regional adaptation of carbon farming	Fragmented governance; outcomes not systematized into MRV frameworks; weak feedback loops with policy or registries; variable data standards.	Scale up Living Labs via Horizon Europe into standardized MRV pilots; require harmonized outputs (SOC, co-benefits) usable by CRCF certification bodies.	(EU/2021/783, 2021; European Commission, 2024; Granholm et al., 2025)
Carbon Market Platforms (e.g., AGREENA)	Private Restricted (proprietary, case-specific agreements)	~12+ MRV-integrated carbon platforms	Field-level SOC, yields, financial metrics (costs, returns), practice adoption history, farmer-reported and sensor-collected data.	Provide integrated datasets combining agronomic, economic, and biophysical indicators. MRV-linked initiatives rely on their structured reporting to validate carbon removals claimed in voluntary carbon markets.	Action-oriented platforms, linked to carbon markets, integrate economics and agronomic data	Restricted access to proprietary platforms; confidentiality of business models limits MRV transparency; unclear data co-ownership between farmers and aggregators.	Promote fair data sharing frameworks with clear IPR rules; make participation in CRCF registry conditional on transparent MRV compatibility; incentivize open APIs.	(Fantappiè et al., 2025; McDonald et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2025)
Research Infrastructures (eLTER, ICOS)	Public research outputs; data via institutional portals	~80 ICOS observatories & 400+ eLTER sites and platforms	High-frequency GHG fluxes, SOC change rates, soil temperature and moisture, biophysical parameters (via ICOS/eLTER instruments).	Anchor MRV efforts in research-grade observational data and metadata protocols. RIs like ICOS and eLTER underpin calibration and verification chains in CRCF-recognized methodologies and ensure continuity in long-term trends.	High scientific quality; integrated measurements of fluxes, biodiversity, climate variables; independent and neutral sources	Disconnect between research monitoring protocols and certification needs; sparse geographic coverage in some Member States; limited MRV-ready data formats.	Integrate ICOS/eLTER benchmark datasets into CRCF model calibration; extend instrumentation to underrepresented regions; formalize scientific oversight in CRCF regulation.	(EU/2024/3012, 2024; ICOS ERIC, 2019, 2025; Mirtl et al., 2021; Nikolaidis et al., 2021)

3. Discussion

Data Quality and Standardization

Despite the existence of robust soil carbon data infrastructures across Europe, significant variability persists in terms of data quality, precision, and harmonization. Laboratory analyses from public and private sources differ in the use of methods (e.g., dry combustion vs. wet oxidation for SOC determination), sampling depths, and units of measurement. Similarly, spatial resolution ranges from sub-parcel detail in Farm Management Systems (FMIS) to a 1 km² grid in pan-European maps, such as those from SoilGrids (Poggio et al., 2021) or LUCAS (Orgiazzi et al., 2018). While standardization efforts, e.g., ISO 17025 for labs (International Organization for Standardization, 2017), INSPIRE for geospatial data (EU/2007/2, 2007) are ongoing, most data remain incomparable without costly post-processing. This limits the utility of aggregated datasets in MRV schemes and constrains policy alignment under frameworks like the EU CRCF.

Integration and Compatibility

Interoperability remains a core challenge. Many repositories are structured for internal use or sector-specific applications (e.g., agriculture, environmental compliance) and lack standardized APIs or metadata schemas that would allow seamless data integration. Public databases (e.g., ESDAC) often use harmonized formats, but private and regional systems—such as FMIS or Living Labs—rarely adhere to open standards. Incompatibilities in data formats, time-stamping, coordinate reference systems, and even crop classification schemes hinder efforts to link data across platforms for coherent MRV and decision support. While Earth Observation systems such as Copernicus services derived by Sentinels and commercial satellite services have proven interoperability through standardised metadata formats and open-access delivery via platforms like Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem their integration into MRV workflows

remains suboptimal. EO data can serve as a spatial backbone for linking siloed data systems providing harmonised spatial-temporal references critical for MRV alignment. Cross-institutional projects, such as those under Horizon Europe, have begun to bridge these gaps, but durable technical and governance solutions are still underdeveloped.

Strengths and Weaknesses

The strengths of the current ecosystem lie in its diversity and domain-specific expertise. EO technologies bring scalability and repeatability, enabling consistent monitoring across administrative boundaries and underrepresented areas; research infrastructure networks, like ICOS and eLTER, deliver scientific precision and long-term data continuity; and FMIS platforms enable granular, real-time monitoring at the field level. However, each system also has limitations: EO cannot assess below-ground SOC stocks directly and they are often framed as supporting tools rather than recognized as a core component of operational MRV; research infrastructures have limited spatial coverage; and FMIS data remain siloed due to privacy and commercial constraints. Soil laboratory data, while accurate, are often fragmented and inaccessible due to GDPR and ownership issues.

Gaps and Challenges

Geographically, notable gaps remain in Eastern and Southeastern Europe, where fewer long-term monitoring stations and digital farm systems exist. However, a concrete consideration of representativeness (e.g., land use, bio-climate, etc.) would be the right approach to make a well-founded assessment of these gaps. Technologically, there is a lack of harmonized proximal sensing libraries for SOC estimation, and the integration of biodiversity or hydrological co-benefits remains limited. Cost barriers also inhibit frequent soil sampling and analysis, particularly for smallholder farms. The absence of legally binding protocols for sharing private lab data—combined with GDPR complexities—creates legal ambiguity and reduces the completeness of national soil inventories. Another overlooked gap lies in the limited institutional uptake of EO-derived SOC estimation models, despite successful prototypes developed through initiatives such as AgriCarbon-EO (Wijmer et al., 2024), WorldCereal (van Tricht et al., 2023), and

the Copernicus Evolution studies (Cordis, 2024). These EO-based methodologies can complement in-situ and modelled estimates, particularly within quantification frameworks.

Implications for Policy and Research

These limitations directly affect the credibility and scalability of soil carbon accounting in Europe. For CRCF regulation, high-quality and comparable SOC data are required to validate emissions, reductions or removals. Fragmented repositories delay certification processes, limit auditability, and may expose systems to accusations of double-counting or greenwashing. From a research perspective, a lack of harmonized datasets restricts cross-country analyses, limits model calibration efforts, and undermines the development of standardized indicators for soil health.

However, the breadth of existing infrastructure also presents a strong foundation for integrated soil carbon governance. Initiatives like the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO), Living Labs (European Commission, 2024), and the eLTER and ICOS strategy papers (ICOS ERIC, 2019; Mirtl et al., 2021; Nikolaidis et al., 2021) call for centralized data streams, shared protocols, and continuous stakeholder engagement—all aligned with the CRCF regulation.

Opportunities for Improvement

Key recommendations include:

- Developing pan-European standards for lab, EO, and farm data with legal recognition under CRCF regulation - Article 14.
- Funding API development and interoperability pilots under Horizon Europe and CAP strategic plans.
- Creating GDPR-compliant governance models that enable shared use of private lab data for public policy.
- Embedding regional Living Labs as MRV test beds with harmonized data outputs usable by certification bodies.

- Supporting sensor calibration networks, particularly for VIS-NIR-MIR platforms, to enable affordable field-scale MRV.
- Institutionalise EO-derived indicators within CRCF quantification tiers, especially as proxies where field measurements are missing or delayed, and promote their integration into digital MRV dashboards.
- Support the development and operationalisation of EO-based Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), EO data cubes, and fusion platforms to enable spatial and temporal harmonisation across farm-level records, laboratory results, and policy reporting systems.

4. Conclusion

Europe stands at a pivotal moment to transform its fragmented soil carbon monitoring landscape into a coherent, harmonised, scalable, and credible system that supports both climate action and sustainable land management. Emerging technologies such as proximal sensing, remote sensing, and AI-assisted data integration offer immense potential to enhance spatial resolution, reduce monitoring costs, and streamline MRV processes. However, their impact will depend on coordinated calibration efforts, shared data standards, and regulatory alignment.

Earth Observation, though currently underrepresented within institutional MRV frameworks, holds considerable promise for enabling scalable, transparent, and cost-effective SOC monitoring. Its open-access nature and capacity to deliver spatially explicit, timely data can complement and reinforce field-based observations and modelling outputs, particularly in data-scarce or cloud-prone regions. A shift from viewing EO as merely supplementary to recognising it as a core operational pillar of MRV would represent a significant step forward for CRCF implementation

Research infrastructure networks (e.g. eLTER, ICOS and various ICPs) are well-positioned to serve as scientific anchors for CRCF-compatible soil carbon validation. Their integration into certification pathways would ensure data transparency, long-term

comparability, and robust uncertainty analysis. In parallel, innovations in data governance—such as blockchain-based custodianship and GDPR-compliant sharing frameworks—could resolve longstanding issues of data ownership and privacy, especially for lab and farm-level data.

The path forward requires cross-sectoral collaboration, strategic investment, and institutional alignment. By embedding these future-focused tools and infrastructures into CRCF implementation and EU Soil Mission policy, Europe can lead globally in evidence-based soil carbon governance and drive measurable climate and ecosystem benefits.

References

- Arias-Navarro, C., Vidojević, D., Zdruli, P., Yunta Mezquita, F., Jones, A [Arwyn], & Wojda, P. (2024). *Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) implementation and LUCAS data integration feasibility in the Western Balkans*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/300751>
- Cordis. (2024). *Copernicus evolution: Research activities in support of the evolution of the Copernicus services | Programme | H2020 | CORDIS | European Commission*. Publication Office/CORDIS. https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_LC-SPACE-18-EO-2020
- EU/2007/2. (2007). *Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE)*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/oj>
- EU/2019/1024. (2019). *Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast)*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>
- EU/2021/2115. (2021). *Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy (CAP Strategic Plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1305/2013 and (EU) No 1307/2013*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/2115/oj>
- EU/2021/2116. (2021). *Regulation (EU) 2021/2116 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 on the financing, management and monitoring of the common agricultural policy and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1306/2013*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/2116/oj>
- EU/2021/783. (2021). *Regulation (EU) 2021/783 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2021 establishing a Programme for the Environment and*

- Climate Action (LIFE), and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1293/2013 (Text with EEA relevance)*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/783/oj>
- EU/2024/3012. (2024). *Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 establishing a Union certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming and carbon storage in products*. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/3012/oj>
- European Commission. (2024). *The mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' – 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/2272933>
- Fantappiè, M., Tziachris, P., Aschonitis, V., Monhonval, A., Formaglio, G., Thakur, G., Pierre-Philippe, C., Piccini, C., Ilaria Falconi, & Farina, R. (2025). *Barriers and incentives for sharing input-data needed in carbon farming and MRV systems in Europe*. Credible Report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15404523>
- Granhölm, K., Bullová, T., & Ács, D. (2025). *Conceptualizing fit-for-region carbon farming for the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15387828>
- ICOS ERIC (2019). ICOS Strategy. <https://www.icos-cp.eu/sites/default/files/cmis/ICOS%20Strategy.pdf>
- ICOS ERIC. (2025). *Station map*. <https://www.icos-cp.eu/station-map>
- International Organization for Standardization. (2017). *ISO/IEC 17025:2017 General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories*. <https://www.iso.org/standard/66912.html>
- Mal, M. (2025). *An effective policy mix for scaling up carbon farming (Full report)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15393725>
- McDonald, H., Pazmino Murillo, J., & Scheid, A. (2024). *Ensuring carbon farming delivers sustainability benefits*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258580>
- Miguel-Lago, M [Mónica], Hermes, M., & Walker, T. (2024). *Earth Observation for the Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification of Carbon Farming*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18339460>

- Mirtl, M., Kaukolehto, M., Bäck, J., & Futter, M. (2021). *Roadmap for European and global partnerships*. eLTER PPP Deliverable 1.3.
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871126/results>
- Nikolaidis, N., Orenstein, D., Choler, P., Bäck, J., Barov, B., Brown, M., Dirnböck, T., Gaillardet, J., Haubold, H., Rennie, S., Watkins, J., Kaukolehto, M., & Michael, M. (2021). *Elter PPP Deliverable D1.1 - eLTER RI Strategic Plan*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10639116>
- Orgiazzi, A., Ballabio, C [C.], Panagos, P., Jones, A [A.], & Fernández-Ugalde, O. (2018). LUCAS Soil, the largest expandable soil dataset for Europe: a review. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 69(1), 140–153.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12499>
- Panagos, P., van Liedekerke, M., Borrelli, P., Köninger, J., Ballabio, C [Cristiano], Orgiazzi, A., Lugato, E., Liakos, L., Hervas, J., Jones, A [Arwyn], & Montanarella, L. (2022). European Soil Data Centre 2.0: Soil data and knowledge in support of the EU policies. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 73(6), Article e13315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13315>
- Poggio, L., Sousa, L. M. de, Batjes, N. H., Heuvelink, G. B. M., Kempen, B., Ribeiro, E., & Rossiter, D. (2021). SoilGrids 2.0: producing soil information for the globe with quantified spatial uncertainty. *SOIL*, 7(1), 217–240.
<https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-7-217-2021>
- Rajewicz, P., & Atherton, J. (2025). *Proximal sensing in carbon farming*. CREDIBLE Report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15388010>
- Shocc, D., & Swails, E. (2024). *VM0042, methodology for improved agricultural land management, version 2.1*. Verra, Verified Carbon Standard.
https://verra.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/VM0042v2.1_ImprovedALM_corrected_21Jan2025.pdf
- Succurro, A., Lawson, G., Boussange, T., Miguel-Lago, M [Monica], Hermes, M., Walker, T., Ceschia, E., Fjaeraa, A. M., Acutis, M., Dubois, A., Bhatnagar, S., Sturrock, H., Luleva, M., Marques, K., & Fantappiè, M. (2025). *Earth Observation (EO) for Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) of Carbon*

Farming (CF) - Uncertainty and Benchmarking. CREDIBLE Report.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15323417>

Tóth, K., & Milenov, P. (2020). *Technical guidelines on IACS spatial data sharing* (JRC technical report JRC121450). Europäische Kommission.

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f09b0355-f7c5-11ea-991b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> <https://doi.org/10.2760/180713>

van Tricht, K., Degerickx, J., Gilliams, S., Zanaga, D., Savinaud, M., Battude, M., Buguet de Chargère, R., Dubreule, G., Grosu, A., Brombacher, J., Pelgrum, H., Lesiv, M., Bayas, J. C. L., Karanam, S., Fritz, S., Becker-Reshef, I., Franch, B., Bononad, B. M., Cintas, J., . . . Szantoi, Z. (2023). *Esa WorldCereal 10 m 2021 v100*. Zenodo. <https://pure.iiasa.ac.at/id/eprint/18989/>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7875105>

Wijmer, T., Al Bitar, A., Arnaud, L., Fieuzal, R., & Geschia, E. (2024). Agricarbon-EO v1.0.1: Large-scale and high-resolution simulation of carbon fluxes by assimilation of Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 reflectances using a Bayesian approach. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 17(3), 997–1021.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-17-997-2024>

Xu, H., D'Hose, T., Deroo, E., Lanckriet, E., Fantappiè, M., Monhonval, A., Aschonitis, V., Schulz, W., Sadowski, S., & Ruyschaert, G. (2025). *Unlocking data for MRV: Data sharing for effective carbon farming*. CREDIBLE Report.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102057>

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming

Funded by
the European Union